

Energy $\rightarrow \hbar/\Delta t$ and Momentum $\rightarrow \hbar/\Delta x$ from $E = pc + m_0c^2$? Part 2

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In Part I, we argued that special relativity implies the existence of two sets of variables, Δx , Δt and Δx_1 , Δt_1 . The two sets represent different physical phenomena. In particular, Δx , Δt is associated with 2-slit interference (for photons and $m_0 > 0$), and Δx_1 and Δt_1 with Newtonian constant speed motion, again for photons and $m_0 > 0$.

The point we wish to make here is that both Δx , Δt and Δx_1 , Δt_1 exist in the same x - t space. Originally, Newtonian mechanics only dealt with one set, Δx_1 , Δt_1 and deterministic motion. This begs the question: Why is Newtonian mechanics not used also for Δx and Δt ? We argue that Δx and Δt are tiny intervals which are linked with $1/p$ and $1/E$ (p =momentum, E =free particle energy) and are associated with stochastic interactions with physical lengths in space (or in time) of order \hbar/p or \hbar/E , hence 2-slit interference. Given the stochastic nature of these interactions they cannot be described in terms of deterministic equations, i.e. $x(t)$.

The next step seems then to divide interactions into two sets, Newtonian deterministic $x_1(t_1)$ behaviour, and the stochastic Δx , Δt considerations which presumably are not readily seen on a macroscopic scale and so were not described by Newton. Such an argument, however, calls for an identification of observable variables. The Δx , Δt scheme does not link $x(t)$ and so spatial 2-slit type experiments need to be described in terms of a kind of spatial probability which shows $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and does not include time. The x which appears in such a picture is the regular x of space, but now it is understood that this space is broken into \hbar/p units. This seems fine except for the problem that one may introduce a spatial probability into Newtonian mechanics, namely $P(x)dx = dx/L$ for constant p , velocity motion. If $P(x)$ is used for a Newtonian picture, then what is the so-called probability function used in the Δx , Δt 2-slit interference scheme? It seems that there must be some link and as one cannot have completely contradicting results.

We argue that Δx and Δt are based on subdividing time and space into intrinsic units based on \hbar/p and \hbar/E . As a result, a probability scheme for Δx , Δt must explicitly display such gradations and there seem to be physical consequences due to these finite gradations. One expects a periodic function which is linear in x and t . At the same time $P(x)$ for Δx_1 and Δt_1 also exists and both probabilities are linked with equal weighting in x and t . As a result, we argue that one must connect the two, with the Δx , Δt probability containing more information than the $P(x)$ one. We suggest that the mathematical process of doing this seems to lead to free particle quantum mechanics and involves a periodic transformation undoing the periodic probability linked with Δx , hence the idea of $W^*(x)W(x) = P(x)$ in quantum mechanics.

Special Relativity and Two Sets of Variables: Δx , Δt and Δx_1 , Δt_1

In Part I, we argued that special relativity implies two sets of spatial-temporal gradations, namely:

Delta x, delta t linked with the physical stochastic result of 2-slit interference ((1a))

Delta x1, delta t1 linked with the physical deterministic result of $x=vt$ for $v=\text{constant}$ ((1b))

Special relativity applies to both photons and particles with rest mass, $m_0 > 0$, as do ((1a)) and ((1b)). Newtonian mechanics only deals with ((1b)), yet Newton argued for light acting as a particle and then in the early 1800s it was found that it undergoes 2-slit interference etc, and was called a wave. According to Part 1, it seems that both photons and particles with $m_0 > 0$ exhibit both features, i.e. the particle-wave duality.

One may then argue that given the two schemes ((1a)), which is stochastic, and ((1b)), which is deterministic, all one need do is establish two sets of mechanics. Newtonian mechanics describes ((1b)) and so only ((1a)) has to be accounted for. ((1a)) is stochastic as $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ suggests a built-in gradation in space and time for a particle with E and hence an uncertainty within these regions. As a result, it seems one simply needs to create a spatial (and separately a temporal) probability function (because there is no $x(t)$) which demonstrates these gradations. Then, Newtonian type interactions which are not affected by $\Delta x, \Delta t$ are handled by Newtonian mechanics and interactions which are, by this new scheme. In other words, one might argue that the two are mutually exclusive.

Unfortunately that is not the case. First of all, as is well known from quantum scattering, interactions with classical Newtonian potentials exhibit effects due to Δx and Δt . These, however, are detected at very small scales. An immediate problem, however, is that one may create a Newtonian spatial probability function:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad ((2)) \quad (\text{for constant } p, v)$$

which means that Newtonian mechanics may also be linked to probability. Thus, one may not argue that ((1a)) is strictly stochastic and ((1b)), strictly deterministic.

In the case of ((2)), there is no information about $\Delta x = \hbar/p$. As we have argued previously, there are two sets of spatial probability and they should be linked. Here we ask: Why should they be linked? Why not simply argue that Newtonian mechanics is deterministic, but allows for a spatial probability ((2)), while ((1a)) is strictly probabilistic and deals with a different probability function based on Δx . If Δx is relevant in a problem, one uses the probability scheme associated with ((1a)), otherwise one uses Newtonian mechanics and ((2)) if necessary. There should be a reason that the two probability schemes must be linked.

Perhaps an answer to this question is that there is one $x-t$ space and even though a probability scheme linked with ((1a)) is based on $\Delta x = \hbar/p$, it still contains the variable x which appears in ((2)). As a result, a probability function linked with ((1a)) cannot contradict ((2)), even though it may be associated with more information. Thus, we argue that there should exist some kind of mathematical mapping of a probability scheme for ((1a)) to ((2)), but it is not clear what such a mapping should be.

Periodicity

Both ((2)) and a probability scheme for ((1a)) should respect the equal weight feature of x space (a t -space), i.e. there is linearity in x and t . ((1a)) is based on $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/p$ and so at the same time one expects periodicity linked to a linear x and a linear p .

Periodicity is linked to motion in a circle which is described by $\exp(i b \theta)$. Here θ is the linear variable and b is linked with the period. Mathematically, this would suggest an $\exp(ipx)$, but this is a complex function, i.e. does not seem physically observable.

Alternatively, there exist many real periodic functions linear in px , including $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ from $\exp(ipx)$. Another example is a square-wave which treats each x with the same weight except at $x=n \cdot \hbar/p$ points. Such a real probability function, however, is completely different from ((2)). If the square wave or even $\sin(px)$ is used, one would require a periodic transformation because for $(\Delta x)/2$, the periodic function is positive and then for the next $.5 \Delta x$, negative. Transforming to ((2)) requires the periodic function and a periodic transformation based on the periodic function. This is, in a sense, already introducing the idea of:

$P(x) = \text{periodic function} \cdot \text{periodic transformation}$ linked to periodic function squared ((3))

Thus, the notion of the probability for ((1a)) somehow being squared to obtain $P(x)$ arises as one must undo the periodicity. As a result, we suggest the mathematical procedure:

$P(x) = \exp(-ipx) / \sqrt{L} \exp(ipx) / \sqrt{L}$ ((4))

There is one x - t space which applies to both $P(x)$ (Newtonian mechanics) and the probabilistic scheme of ((1a)), i.e. a 2-slit apparatus exists in usual Newtonian space. The probability scheme linked to ((1a)) must be periodic in \hbar/p , \hbar/E and is also forced to transform somehow into ((2)). This requires a periodic probability and a periodic transformation to undo the periodicity and so leads to ((4)). Thus, ((4)) is a mathematical mapping between two probability schemes in the same x space.

The question then becomes: Are there any physical examples which support such a viewpoint? We argue that there are and mention one dimensional reflection-refraction which holds for both photons and particles with $m_0 > 0$.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

The Newtonian probability ((2)) is not particularly informative given that it is a constant. One might even suggest that it be ignored and hence bypass all of the arguments leading to ((4)). An interesting example, however, appears in nature, and even in the macroscopic world, namely one dimensional reflection-refraction (e.g. light reflecting and refracting from a window). This problem also exists for $m_0 > 0$. Given that ((2)) is a probability in space, there is no time present. One does not follow a single photon in time and note whether it reflects or refracts, rather one

considers steady streams of reflected and refracted (and incident) photons. The issue is that they have different weights and Newtonian mechanics does not indicate what these weights should be.

The question becomes: Does the $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ scheme shed any light on the problem? The probability in this case is the complex function $\exp(ipx)$, which is not a usual physical observable. As we have argued many times before, one may match $\exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative at $x=0$ to obtain two solutions in two unknowns if one assigns a weight of 1 to the incident photon. I.e. $E=pc$ and E is the same for all:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((5a)) \text{ and}$$

$$Ap \exp(ipx) - pB \exp(-ipx) = cp_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((5b)) \quad p_2 = n_2 p \text{ and } n_1=1 \quad c_2=c/n_2.$$

Using $A=1$, one may solve for B and C . Multiplying ((5a)) by ((5b)) yields:

$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2$ suggesting that AA, BB, CC are physical fluxes. Thus, one sees an example in nature of Newtonian probability linked directly to the probability scheme of ((1a)) which is required to solve the problem.

Quantum Mechanics

As a result, $\exp(ipx) \exp(-iEt)$ is a mathematical probability which allows one to solve problems which are affected by Δx , Δt . This probability is complex and not linked to a physical observable (although the literature has examples of attempts to directly measure $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$). If one has a complex probability, then one must also have observables which one may measure. Newtonian mechanics, which is measurable, allows for a probability $P(x)$ which is directly measurable. Mapping $\exp(ipx) \exp(-iEt)$ to $P(x) P_1(t)$ yields a measurable probability which erases, as much as possible, the gradations \hbar/p , \hbar/E . In some cases, however, when interference occurs, the gradation signatures remain.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I, we argued that there are two gradation schemes for Δt and Δx , namely Δx , Δt (linked with 2-slit interference) and Δx_1 , Δt_1 , linked with constant motion. For a particle with $m_0 > 0$, these are different. For the $m_0 > 0$ and photon case, one has $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$. The Δx , Δt scheme is linked with stochastic interactions in 2-slit type situations etc. As a result, one might suggest that Newtonian mechanics be applied to Δx_1 , Δt_1 cases which are deterministic [$x_1(t_1)$] and that a probability scheme be developed for the Δx , Δt case.

One might suggest that the two schemes are mutually exclusive. We argue that this is not the case. In fact, the Newtonian scheme allows for $P(x) dx = dx/L$ for a constant velocity, where L is an arbitrary length. Whatever scheme is used for the probability of Δx , it cannot contradict $P(x)=1/L$ (at least on average). This suggests a math transformation from the Δx probability to $P(x)=1/L$. The Δx probability must be periodic in px (linear space) and so the transformation itself must be periodic to undo the periodicity of the probability. This suggests a

squaring so-to-speak of the probability linked with Δx in order to obtain $P(x)=1/L$. This, in turn, leads to the quantum $W^*(x)W(x) = P(x)$ case. As experimental verification, we cite the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem.